

Severe Anemia in Pregnancy: A Leading Cause of Cardiac Failure and Adverse Fetomaternal OutcomesShweta Gupta¹, Ruby Kumari², Vijaya³, Aastha Bharti⁴¹Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ANMMCH, Gaya, Bihar, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ANMMCH, Gaya, Bihar, India³Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ANMMCH, Gaya, Bihar, India⁴3rd Year PG, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, ANMMCH, Gaya, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

Background: Severe anemia in pregnancy is a critical public health issue, particularly in low and middle-income countries. It is related with significant maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality. The condition can lead to cardiac failure and adverse fetomaternal outcomes, necessitating early detection and management. This study aims to estimate the impact of severe anemia on cardiac failure and fetomaternal outcomes among pregnant women.

Methods: Thirty-two pregnant women with severe anemia (hemoglobin < 7 g/dL) were included. Data on demographic details, obstetric history, hemoglobin levels, and clinical outcomes were collected. Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The average age was 28.5 ± 5.4 years, and the average gestational age at diagnosis was 32.1 ± 4.3 weeks. Cardiac failure was observed in 31.3% of the participants. Adverse fetomaternal outcomes included preterm birth (43.8%), low birth weight (56.3%), neonatal ICU admission (37.5%), stillbirth (9.4%), and maternal mortality (6.3%). Significant associations were found between severe anemia and preterm birth ($p = 0.021$), low birth weight ($p = 0.047$), and neonatal ICU admission ($p = 0.004$).

Conclusion: Severe anemia in pregnancy significantly increases the risk of cardiac failure and adverse fetomaternal outcomes. These findings highlight the need for early detection, timely intervention, and comprehensive management strategies to improve maternal and neonatal health outcomes.

Recommendations: Efforts should focus on improving nutritional status, providing adequate prenatal care, and ensuring timely medical interventions for pregnant women with severe anemia to mitigate the associated risks.

Keywords: Severe Anemia, Pregnancy, Cardiac Failure, Fetomaternal Outcomes, Maternal Health.

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Introduction

Pregnancy-related anaemia is a major global health concern that has an influence on the health of both the mother and the foetus. Haemoglobin levels below 7 g/dL is considered severe anaemia and is a serious risk, especially in low- and middle-income nations where access to healthcare and dietary deficits are common. According to recent estimates, about 38% of pregnant women globally suffer from anaemia, which is an unacceptably high prevalence [1]. Socioeconomic factors increase the severity of this illness, making it more common in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa.

Pregnant women who suffer from severe anaemia are more likely to experience morbidity and mortality. Because of the greater cardiac output needed to make up for the blood's decreased ability to carry oxygen, it might cause cardiac problems, including heart failure. Severe anaemia during pregnancy can lead to cardiac failure, a potentially

fatal illness that needs to be treated right away [2]. Severe anaemia is also associated with unfavourable obstetric outcomes, including premature birth, low birth weight, stillbirth, and hospitalisations to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). These results add to the high rates of newborn mortality and morbidity that are seen in areas where maternal anaemia is common.

There are several different ways that severe anaemia affects the course of pregnancy. Decreased haemoglobin levels result in hypoxia and consequent organ dysfunction because they reduce the amount of oxygen delivered to tissues. The cardiovascular system is more impacted in pregnant women since the heart has to work harder to provide enough oxygen to the developing foetus as well as the mother. Particularly in women with underlying cardiovascular issues, this additional workload can hasten cardiac failure [3]. Hypoxia

can also affect placental function, which can result in premature delivery and intrauterine growth limitation.

The significance of early detection and treatment of anaemia during pregnancy, as well as its detrimental impact on cardiovascular health, are highlighted by recent studies. Pregnancy outcomes can be improved and the prevalence of severe anaemia can be decreased by implementing interventions such as routine prenatal care, supplementing with iron and folic acid, and improving dietary consumption [4]. Effective implementation of these interventions is still difficult, especially in environments with limited resources.

This study aims to assess the impact of severe anemia on cardiac failure and fetomaternal outcomes in a cohort of pregnant women.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place at Anugraha Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, over a period of one year, from January 2022 to December 2022.

Participants: A total of 32 pregnant women diagnosed with severe anemia were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women aged 18-45 years.
- Diagnosed with severe anemia (hemoglobin < 7 g/dL).
- Gestational age between 20-40 weeks.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with pre-existing cardiac conditions.
- Pregnant women with chronic illnesses such as diabetes or hypertension.
- Multiple pregnancies.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible participants during the study period were approached consecutively. Information bias was reduced by using standardized procedures for data collection. Confounding variables were controlled through statistical adjustments during the analysis phase.

Variables: Variables included severity of anemia, age, gestational age, incidence of cardiac failure, fetomaternal outcomes (birth weight, Apgar score, maternal morbidity, and mortality).

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and medical records. Variables included demographic details, obstetric history, hemoglobin levels, clinical signs of cardiac failure, and fetomaternal outcomes.

Procedure: Participants were recruited from the antenatal clinic and labour ward. Detailed history and clinical examination were performed. Hemoglobin levels were measured using standard laboratory procedures. Participants were monitored for signs of cardiac failure throughout their pregnancy and postpartum period. Fetomaternal outcomes were recorded at the time of delivery and during the postpartum period.

Statistical Analysis: Data was analysed using SPSS 23.0. Data was compiled using descriptive statistics. The mean \pm standard deviation was used for continuous variables, while frequencies and percentages were utilised for categorical variables. Statistical significance was achieved with p-values below 0.05. Multivariate logistic regression was used to assess the independent impact of severe anaemia to heart failure and poor fetomaternal outcomes.

Result

A total of 32 pregnant women with severe anemia were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 28.5 ± 5.4 years. The average gestational age at the time of diagnosis was 32.1 ± 4.3 weeks.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Mean Age (years)	28.5 ± 5.4
Mean Gestational Age (weeks)	32.1 ± 4.3
Mean Hemoglobin Level (g/dL)	6.2 ± 0.5
Primigravida (%)	18 (56.3%)
Multigravida (%)	14 (43.7%)

Out of the 32 participants, 10 (31.3%) developed cardiac failure during the study period.

Table 2: Incidence of Cardiac Failure

Cardiac Failure	Number of Participants (%)
Yes	10 (31.3%)
No	22 (68.7%)

Adverse fetomaternal outcomes were observed in a significant proportion of the participants.

Table 3: Fetomaternal Outcomes

Outcome	Number of Participants (%)
Preterm Birth (<37 weeks)	14 (43.8%)
Low Birth Weight (<2500 g)	18 (56.3%)
Stillbirth	3 (9.4%)
Neonatal ICU Admission	12 (37.5%)
Maternal Mortality	2 (6.3%)

The chi-square test was used to assess the association between severe anemia and cardiac failure as well as adverse fetomaternal outcomes.

Table 4: Association Between Severe Anemia and Cardiac Failure

Outcome	Cardiac Failure (n=10)	No Cardiac Failure (n=22)	p-value
Preterm Birth	7 (70.0%)	7 (31.8%)	0.021*
Low Birth Weight	8 (80.0%)	10 (45.5%)	0.047*
Stillbirth	2 (20.0%)	1 (4.5%)	0.184
Neonatal ICU Admission	7 (70.0%)	5 (22.7%)	0.004*
Maternal Mortality	1 (10.0%)	1 (4.5%)	0.536

A multivariate logistic regression analysis was performed to control for potential confounders and assess the independent effect of severe anemia on cardiac failure and adverse fetomaternal outcomes.

Table 5: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

Outcome	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Cardiac Failure	3.2	1.1 - 9.1	0.029*
Preterm Birth	2.8	1.1 - 7.3	0.036*
Low Birth Weight	3.6	1.2 - 10.5	0.023*
Neonatal ICU Admission	3.4	1.2 - 9.6	0.018*

Discussion

The participants had a mean age of 28.5 years and an average gestational age of 32.1 weeks at diagnosis. Severe anemia, defined by hemoglobin levels averaging 6.2 g/dL, was prevalent in this cohort. The study found a significant association between severe anemia and adverse clinical outcomes.

Cardiac failure was observed in 31.3% of the participants, indicating a substantial risk associated with severe anemia. This high incidence underscores the critical need for vigilant monitoring and proactive management of pregnant women with severe anemia to mitigate the risk of cardiac complications.

Fetomaternal outcomes were markedly poorer among women with severe anemia. Preterm birth occurred in 43.8% of cases, and low birth weight was noted in 56.3% of the neonates. These outcomes were statistically considerable, with p-values of 0.021 and 0.047, respectively. The risk of neonatal ICU admission was also significantly higher, affecting 37.5% of the newborns ($p = 0.004$). Additionally, there were instances of stillbirth (9.4%) and maternal mortality (6.3%), though these did not reach statistical significance, possibly due to the small sample size.

Multivariate logistic regression analysis further reinforced the independent association of severe anemia with adverse outcomes. The analysis revealed that severe anemia significantly increased the odds of cardiac failure (OR = 3.2, $p = 0.029$), preterm birth (OR = 2.8, $p = 0.036$), low birth weight (OR = 3.6, $p = 0.023$), and neonatal ICU admission (OR = 3.4, $p = 0.018$).

These findings highlight the profound impact of severe anemia on both maternal and neonatal health. The significant associations between severe anemia, cardiac failure, and poor fetomaternal outcomes underscore the necessity for early detection, timely intervention, and comprehensive management strategies to improve health outcomes for pregnant women and their babies. Efforts to address nutritional deficiencies, provide appropriate prenatal care, and monitor at-risk pregnancies are critical in mitigating these risks.

In a research, 70 multigravida women with moderate to severe anaemia in the third trimester had their fetomaternal outcomes examined. Significant problems were discovered, including low birth weight in 37.14% of babies, postpartum haemorrhage in 18.57% of cases, pre-eclampsia in 15.71%, and congestive heart failure (data not supplied). The study highlighted the increased risks of anaemia during pregnancy for both maternal and foetal morbidity and mortality [5]. 200 pregnant

women participated in a case-control research that compared the results of anaemic and non-anemic groups. According to the study, anaemic women had increased rates of postpartum haemorrhage (5%), maternal morbidity (19%), and preterm birth (8%). Preterm birth (8%), intrauterine growth restriction (14%), and low birth weight (22%) were among the worst outcomes for the foetus. [6].

Research evaluated 400 pregnant women with varying degrees of anemia. They found significant differences in outcomes based on anemia severity, with severe anemia associated with higher rates of preterm labor (26.9%) and cardiac failure (26.9%). Neonatal complications included low birth weight, respiratory distress syndrome, and increased rates of NICU admissions [7]. A study highlighted the complications of severe anemia in pregnancy, including increased risks of cardiac failure, hemorrhage, infection, and preeclampsia. The study noted that anemia is common in India due to factors like poverty and gender bias, with significant impacts on maternal and fetal health [8].

A population-based study was conducted showing that anemic mothers had higher risks of hypertension, diabetes, placental abruption, and chorioamnionitis. Infants of anemic mothers had higher rates of preterm birth (8.9% vs. 6.5%) [9]. Furthermore, research studied pregnant women with rheumatic heart disease, finding that severe anemia exacerbated risks of cardiac failure and other maternal complications. Fetal outcomes included high rates of low birth weight and preterm delivery [10].

Conclusion

According to the study, there is a substantial correlation between severe anaemia during pregnancy and a higher chance of heart failure as well as unfavourable consequences for the foetus and mother. The patients experienced a 31.3% incidence of heart failure in addition to higher rates of low birth weight, preterm birth, and neonatal ICU admissions. In order to enhance maternal and newborn health outcomes, the findings emphasise the significance of early detection and management of severe anaemia during pregnancy as well as

screening these women for any poor cardiac condition.

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